

Title Page:

Google Drive as Free Electronic Medical Record system in Resource-Constrained Intensive Care Unit

Keywords: EMR, Google Drive, ICU

Abstract:

EMRs are a digitalized format of patient information that includes symptoms, co-morbidities, investigative patterns, clinical imaging, and management throughout time. Due to our institute's understanding of offline data management, which includes a specialised Medical Record Department to preserve the files and records of discharged and demised patients, we suffered significant time delays in keeping track of their follow-ups.

For keeping track of our patients, we designed the most basic cloud storage solution, Google Drive, which is free and accessible on all platforms.

Body of Manuscript:

Electronic Medical Records (EMR) are a digitalized format of patient data that includes symptoms, co-morbidities, investigation trends, clinical imaging, and management throughout time. The usage of electronic medical records (EMR) increases the efficiency and safety of healthcare services.¹ Many EMR software are available, but the majority of them have significant upfront and ongoing expenditures. They also have a number of drawbacks, such as not being tailored to the needs of digitally illiterate users and imposing a rigid data entry format. Again, cross-platform availability is limited, and there are fewer EMR software designed specifically for ICUs.²

We experienced considerable time delays in keeping track of our patients' follow-up due to our institute's understanding of offline data management, which includes a specialised Medical Record Department to preserve the files and records of discharged and demised patients.

Because necessity is the mother of invention, we devised the simplest cloud storage system, Google Drive, which is available to anyone on all devices for free for maintaining our patient records.

The Design-

We created a Gmail account for our ICU and provided the login information to the residents. Next, we created a folder for the current year and added month-specific folders to it. Each month's folder now contained separate folders for each of our three ICU pods, namely cubicles 1, 2, and 3. Each month's folder contained two folders of deaths and discharges, both of which had a subfolder of system-wise principal disorders such as ARDS, Sepsis, Neurology, Neurosurgery, Trauma, Cardiology, Post-operative, and so on. There were different folders for each patient in each cubicle's folder. Aside from a Google Document for daily notes and a Google Sheet for inputting daily investigation trends, each patient's folder contained named subfolders for their receiving notes, clinical photos, and culture reports.

The Workflow-

Whenever a new patient is admitted, a folder for him or her is created in the cubicle folder. The resident takes a picture of the receiving notes with the handwritten history on his phone and uploads it to the receiving notes folder. In the Google Sheet, prior research trends, as well as future investigation trends, are recorded. Any additional clinical photos, such as echocardiography, lung ultrasound images, or chest x-rays, are taken using a mobile phone and saved in the patient's clinical images folder with the date listed in the file name. Every

shift, a brief note on the discussed long-term objective and short-term plan, as well as any noteworthy events that occurred and management changes, is placed in the daily notes document of the particular patient via computer or mobile phone in a time-ordered manner. Every morning round, a printed compilation of the previous day's daily notes is handed over to all beds as condensed handover notes. Any additional plans for the day are scribbled on the page. The studies, as well as clinical photographs, are conveniently accessible both at the bedside and remotely during the discussion. When a patient is discharged or dies, the patient's folder is moved to the month's discharge and death summary folders, along with the discharge summary or death summary. Any culture reports for patients are uploaded to the patient's folder in a date-ordered format.

Implications:

In a resource-constrained environment, this use of freely available cloud services, which allow for the flexibility of storing both traditional handwritten and typed notes, provides even the most technologically inept member of the team with a quick manner of keeping records.³ This record-keeping aids in timely audits as well as the preservation of cases as case reports for future reference. This method isn't flawless, and it has a number of drawbacks, including the fact that it isn't HIPAA-compliant, and problems regarding data security may arise. However, Google is a firm that can be trusted when it comes to data security. This method is extremely adaptable, allowing users to customise it to their specific needs, and this is where the main strength of this data management system lies. We hope that countries with limited resources adopt this approach as their own cloud-based Electronic Medical Record system.

Author's Contributions:

1. Abhijeet Anand, Conceptualization & implementation of the idea plus First author of the article. (Corresponding Author), Senior Resident, Anaesthesia & Critical Care, AIIMS, Bhopal, India email - abhijeet.anand@hotmail.com
2. Saiteja Kodamanchili, Running the project and devising solutions to problems faced plus proofreading of article.
3. Rajesh Panda, Proofreading and editing the paper.
4. Gowthaman TB, Running the project and providing inputs to the article as well as the project design.
5. Krishnkant Bhardwaj, Providing inputs to the project as a person with less technical acumen and thus improving the project design and article to be more sensitive to such personal limitations.
6. Pradeep Moolchandani, Participated in data entry and gave inputs to refine the workflow and did proofreading of the grammar of the paper.

Acknowledgements:

Saurabh Saigal, in Charge of ICU, allowed us all to start and run the project successfully.

Statement on conflicts of interest:

No conflict of interest of any member of team.

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Figure:

FIGURE 1: Dendrogram Of Individual Folders in Google Drive

